

Designs Invariant under Simple Groups: MAGMA Computations

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Abstract

In this note, we provide designs that are invariant under finite simple groups. Each chapter includes a theorem upon which the computations are based. Some of these designs have been mentioned in earlier papers, while others have been computed directly by the author. This document will be updated regularly, so readers should take note of the most recent version to ensure they have the most complete information and to correct any possible errors.

Designs from Conjugacy Classes and Maximal Subgroups

Theorem. (Saeidi, Saydi, Seretlo 2024) Let G be a finite group and H be a subgroup of G . For $x \in G$, let x^G be a conjugacy class of G , and let

$$\mathcal{B} = \{T^g | g \in G\},$$

where $T = x^H$. If $T \neq \emptyset$, then we can construct a

$$1 - (|x^G|, |T|, \frac{|C_G(x):C_H(x)|}{|N_G(T):H|})$$

design $\mathcal{D}(T)$. Moreover, G acts transitively on both points and blocks of $\mathcal{D}(T)$.

Corollary. (Saeidi, Saydi, Seretlo) If H is a maximal subgroup of G and $x^H \neq \emptyset$, then we can construct a

$$1 - (|x^G|, |x^H|, \frac{C_G(x)}{C_H(x)})$$

design.

Designs from the Janko group J_1

Table 1: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 266

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 11, 2)$ $1 - (1463, 132, 24)$ $1 - (1463, 660, 120)$	$1 - (1463, 55, 10)$ $1 - (1463, 165, 30)$	$1 - (1463, 110, 20)$ $1 - (1463, 330, 60)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 110, 5)$ $1 - (5852, 660, 30)$	$1 - (5852, 132, 6)$	$1 - (5852, 330, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 220, 2)$ $1 - (29060, 110, 1)$	$1 - (29260, 330, 3)$	$1 - (29260, 660, 6)$
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (29280, 660, 7)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 132, 2)$	$1 - (17556, 330, 5)$	$1 - (17556, 660, 10)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 60, 1)$ $1 - (15960, 660, 11)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 132, 3)$	$1 - (11704, 220, 5)$	$1 - (11704, 660, 15)$
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 660, 19)$		

Table 2: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1045

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 7, 5)$ $1 - (1463, 168, 120)$	$1 - (1463, 56, 40)$	$1 - (1463, 84, 60)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 28, 5)$ $1 - (5852, 168, 30)$	$1 - (5852, 56, 10)$	$1 - (5852, 84, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 28, 1)$ $1 - (29260, 168, 6)$	$1 - (29260, 56, 2)$	$1 - (29260, 84, 3)$
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (25080, 24, 1)$ $1 - (25080, 168, 7)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 84, 5)$	$1 - (17556, 168, 10)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 168, 11)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 56, 5)$	$1 - (11704, 168, 15)$	
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 168, 19)$		

Table 3: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1463

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 1, 1)$ $1 - (1463, 20, 20)$	$1 - (1463, 12, 12)$ $1 - (1463, 60, 60)$	$1 - (1463, 15, 15)$ $1 - (1463, 120, 120)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 12, 3)$ $1 - (5852, 120, 30)$	$1 - (5852, 20, 5)$	$1 - (5852, 60, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 20, 1)$ $1 - (29260, 120, 6)$	$1 - (29260, 40, 2)$	$1 - (29260, 60, 3)$
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (25080, 120, 7)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 12, 1)$ $1 - (17556, 120, 10)$	$1 - (17556, 24, 2)$	$1 - (17556, 60, 5)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 120, 11)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 24, 3)$	$1 - (11704, 40, 5)$	$1 - (11704, 120, 15)$
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 120, 19)$		

Table 4: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1540

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 19, 20)$ $1 - (1463, 114, 120)$	$1 - (1463, 38, 40)$	$1 - (1463, 57, 60)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 19, 5)$ $1 - (5852, 114, 30)$	$1 - (5852, 38, 10)$	$1 - (5852, 57, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 19, 1)$ $1 - (29260, 114, 6)$	$1 - (29260, 38, 2)$	$1 - (29260, 57, 3)$
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (25080, 114, 7)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 57, 5)$	$1 - (17556, 114, 10)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 114, 11)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 38, 5)$	$1 - (11704, 114, 15)$	
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 6, 1)$	$1 - (9240, 114, 19)$	

Table 5: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1596

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 22, 24)$	$1 - (1463, 55, 60)$	$1 - (1463, 110, 120)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 11, 3)$ $1 - (5852, 110, 30)$	$1 - (5852, 22, 6)$	$1 - (5852, 55, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 55, 3)$	$1 - (29260, 110, 6)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (25080, 110, 7)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 11, 1)$ $1 - (17556, 110, 10)$	$1 - (17556, 22, 2)$	$1 - (17556, 55, 5)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 10, 1)$	$1 - (15960, 110, 11)$	
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 22, 3)$	$1 - (11704, 110, 15)$	
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 110, 19)$		

Table 6: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 2926

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 3, 6)$ $1 - (1463, 30, 60)$	$1 - (1463, 5, 10)$ $1 - (1463, 60, 120)$	$1 - (1463, 15, 30)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 2, 1)$	$1 - (5852, 30, 15)$	$1 - (5852, 60, 30)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 10, 1)$	$1 - (29260, 30, 3)$	$1 - (29260, 60, 6)$
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (25080, 60, 7)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 6, 1)$	$1 - (17556, 30, 5)$	$1 - (17556, 60, 10)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 60, 11)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 4, 1)$	$1 - (11704, 60, 15)$	
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 60, 19)$		

Table 7: The designs by J_1 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 4180

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1463, 7, 20)$ $1 - (1463, 42, 120)$	$1 - (1463, 14, 40)$	$1 - (1463, 21, 60)$
$Cl(3), Cl(4), Cl(5)$	$1 - (5852, 7, 5)$ $1 - (5852, 42, 30)$	$1 - (5852, 14, 10)$	$1 - (5852, 21, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (29260, 7, 1)$ $1 - (29260, 42, 6)$	$1 - (29260, 14, 2)$	$1 - (29260, 21, 3)$
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (25080, 6, 1)$	$1 - (25080, 42, 7)$	
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (17556, 21, 5)$	$1 - (17556, 42, 10)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15960, 42, 11)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11704, 14, 5)$	$1 - (11704, 42, 15)$	
$Cl(13), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (9240, 42, 19)$		

Designs from the Janko group J_2

Table 8: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 10080

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 6, 192)$ $1 - (315, 30, 960)$	$1 - (315, 12, 384)$ $1 - (315, 60, 1920)$	$1 - (315, 15, 480)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 10, 40)$ $1 - (2520, 60, 240)$	$1 - (2520, 15, 60)$	$1 - (2520, 30, 120)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 20, 360)$	$1 - (560, 60, 1080)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 20, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 30, 18)$	$1 - (16800, 60, 36)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 60, 96)$		
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 12, 60)$	$1 - (2016, 30, 150)$	$1 - (2016, 60, 300)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 12, 10)$	$1 - (12096, 60, 50)$	
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 60, 24)$		
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 20, 4)$	$1 - (50400, 30, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 60, 12)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 60, 7)$		
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 60, 8)$		
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 30, 10)$	$1 - (30240, 60, 20)$	
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 12, 2)$	$1 - (60480, 60, 10)$	
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 60, 15)$		

Table 9: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 2016

Conjugacy classes $CI(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$CI(2)$	$1 - (315, 15, 96)$	$1 - (315, 75, 480)$	$1 - (315, 150, 960)$
$CI(3)$	$1 - (2520, 15, 12)$ $1 - (2520, 150, 120)$	$1 - (2520, 25, 20)$ $1 - (2520, 300, 240)$	$1 - (2520, 75, 60)$
$CI(4)$	$1 - (560, 30, 108)$	$1 - (560, 50, 180)$	$1 - (560, 150, 540)$
$CI(5)$	$1 - (16800, 50, 6)$ $1 - (16800, 300, 36)$	$1 - (16800, 100, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 150, 18)$
$CI(6)$	$1 - (6300, 150, 48)$	$1 - (6300, 300, 96)$	
$CI(7), CI(8)$	$1 - (2016, 6, 6)$ $1 - (2016, 300, 300)$	$1 - (2016, 60, 60)$	$1 - (2016, 150, 150)$
$CI(9), CI(10)$	$1 - (12096, 6, 1)$ $1 - (12096, 150, 25)$	$1 - (12096, 30, 5)$ $1 - (12096, 300, 50)$	$1 - (12096, 60, 10)$
$CI(11)$	$1 - (25200, 150, 12)$	$1 - (25200, 300, 24)$	
$CI(12), CI(19)$	$1 - (50400, 50, 2)$	$1 - (50400, 150, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 300, 12)$
$CI(13)$	$1 - (86400, 300, 7)$		
$CI(14)$	$1 - (75600, 150, 4)$	$1 - (75600, 300, 8)$	
$CI(15), CI(16)$	$1 - (30240, 30, 2)$	$1 - (30240, 150, 10)$	$1 - (30240, 300, 20)$
$CI(17), CI(18)$	$1 - (60480, 30, 1)$	$1 - (60480, 150, 5)$	$1 - (60480, 300, 10)$
$CI(20), CI(21)$	$1 - (40320, 60, 3)$	$1 - (40320, 300, 15)$	

Table 10: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1800

Conjugacy classes $CI(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$CI(2)$	$1 - (315, 21, 120)$ $1 - (315, 168, 960)$	$1 - (315, 42, 240)$	$1 - (315, 84, 480)$
$CI(3)$	$1 - (2520, 28, 20)$ $1 - (2520, 336, 240)$	$1 - (2520, 84, 60)$	$1 - (2520, 168, 120)$
$CI(4)$	$1 - (560, 14, 45)$ $1 - (560, 84, 270)$	$1 - (560, 42, 135)$ $1 - (560, 168, 540)$	$1 - (560, 56, 180)$
$CI(5)$	$1 - (16800, 56, 6)$ $1 - (16800, 336, 36)$	$1 - (16800, 112, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 168, 18)$
$CI(6)$	$1 - (6300, 42, 12)$ $1 - (6300, 336, 96)$	$1 - (6300, 84, 24)$	$1 - (6300, 168, 48)$
$CI(7), CI(8)$	$1 - (2016, 168, 150)$	$1 - (2016, 336, 300)$	
$CI(9), CI(10)$	$1 - (12096, 168, 25)$	$1 - (12096, 336, 50)$	
$CI(11)$	$1 - (25200, 42, 3)$ $1 - (25200, 336, 24)$	$1 - (25200, 81, 6)$	$1 - (25200, 168, 12)$
$CI(12), CI(19)$	$1 - (50400, 56, 2)$ $1 - (50400, 336, 12)$	$1 - (50400, 84, 3)$	$1 - (50400, 168, 6)$
$CI(13)$	$1 - (86400, 48, 1)$	$1 - (86400, 336, 7)$	
$CI(14)$	$1 - (75600, 42, 1)$ $1 - (75600, 336, 8)$	$1 - (75600, 84, 2)$	$1 - (75600, 168, 4)$
$CI(15), CI(16)$	$1 - (30240, 168, 10)$	$1 - (30240, 336, 20)$	
$CI(17), CI(18)$	$1 - (60480, 168, 5)$	$1 - (60480, 336, 10)$	
$CI(20), CI(21)$	$1 - (40320, 336, 15)$		

Table 11: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1008

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 5, 16)$ $1 - (315, 100, 320)$	$1 - (315, 25, 80)$	$1 - (315, 60, 192)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 15, 6)$ $1 - (2520, 300, 120)$	$1 - (2520, 60, 24)$	$1 - (2520, 75, 30)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 20, 36)$	$1 - (560, 120, 216)$	$1 - (560, 300, 540)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 50, 3)$ $1 - (16800, 600, 36)$	$1 - (16800, 200, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 300, 18)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 100, 16)$ $1 - (6300, 600, 96)$	$1 - (6300, 200, 32)$	$1 - (6300, 300, 48)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 2, 1)$ $1 - (2016, 100, 50)$ $1 - (2016, 300, 150)$	$1 - (2016, 24, 12)$ $1 - (2016, 120, 60)$ $1 - (2016, 600, 300)$	$1 - (2016, 50, 25)$ $1 - (2016, 200, 100)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 12, 1)$ $1 - (12096, 300, 25)$	$1 - (12096, 24, 2)$ $1 - (12096, 600, 50)$	$1 - (12096, 120, 10)$
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 100, 4)$ $1 - (25200, 600, 24)$	$1 - (25200, 200, 8)$	$1 - (25200, 300, 12)$
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 100, 2)$ $1 - (50400, 300, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 150, 3)$ $1 - (50400, 600, 12)$	$1 - (50400, 200, 4)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 600, 7)$		
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 300, 4)$	$1 - (75600, 600, 8)$	
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 30, 1)$ $1 - (30240, 300, 10)$	$1 - (30240, 120, 4)$ $1 - (30240, 600, 20)$	$1 - (30240, 150, 5)$
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 60, 1)$ $1 - (60480, 600, 10)$	$1 - (60480, 120, 2)$	$1 - (60480, 300, 5)$
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 40, 1)$ $1 - (40320, 600, 15)$	$1 - (40320, 120, 3)$	$1 - (40320, 200, 5)$

Table 12: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 840

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 15, 40)$	$1 - (315, 120, 320)$	$1 - (315, 180, 480)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 3, 1)$ $1 - (2520, 72, 24)$ $1 - (2520, 720, 240)$	$1 - (2520, 45, 15)$ $1 - (2520, 180, 60)$	$1 - (2520, 60, 20)$ $1 - (2520, 360, 120)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 4, 6)$ $1 - (560, 360, 540)$	$1 - (560, 60, 90)$	$1 - (560, 72, 108)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 20, 1)$ $1 - (16800, 180, 9)$	$1 - (16800, 60, 3)$ $1 - (16800, 240, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 80, 4)$ $1 - (16800, 720, 36)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 120, 16)$ $1 - (6300, 360, 48)$	$1 - (6300, 180, 24)$ $1 - (6300, 720, 96)$	$1 - (6300, 240, 32)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 12, 5)$ $1 - (2016, 240, 100)$	$1 - (2016, 144, 60)$ $1 - (2016, 720, 300)$	$1 - (2016, 180, 75)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 72, 5)$ $1 - (12096, 720, 50)$	$1 - (12096, 144, 10)$	$1 - (12096, 360, 25)$
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 60, 2)$ $1 - (25200, 360, 12)$	$1 - (25200, 120, 4)$ $1 - (25200, 720, 24)$	$1 - (25200, 180, 6)$
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 60, 1)$ $1 - (50400, 240, 4)$	$1 - (50400, 120, 2)$ $1 - (50400, 360, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 180, 3)$ $1 - (50400, 720, 12)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 720, 7)$		
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 360, 4)$ $1 - (75600, 720, 8)$		
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 36, 1)$ $1 - (30240, 720, 20)$	$1 - (30240, 144, 4)$	$1 - (30240, 180, 5)$
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 360, 5)$ $1 - (60480, 720, 10)$		
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 48, 1)$ $1 - (40320, 720, 15)$	$1 - (40320, 144, 3)$	$1 - (40320, 240, 5)$

Table 13: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 280

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 45, 40)$	$1 - (315, 270, 240)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 36, 4)$	$1 - (2520, 108, 12)$	$1 - (2520, 540, 60)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 2, 1)$ $1 - (560, 270, 135)$	$1 - (560, 36, 18)$	$1 - (560, 216, 108)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 240, 4)$ $1 - (16800, 2160, 36)$	$1 - (16800, 720, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 1080, 18)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 90, 4)$ $1 - (6300, 1080, 48)$	$1 - (6300, 270, 12)$ $1 - (6300, 2160, 96)$	$1 - (6300, 540, 24)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 72, 10)$	$1 - (2016, 432, 60)$	$1 - (2016, 1080, 150)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 216, 5)$ $1 - (12096, 2160, 50)$	$1 - (12096, 432, 10)$	$1 - (12096, 1080, 25)$
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 90, 1)$ $1 - (25200, 1080, 12)$	$1 - (25200, 270, 3)$ $1 - (25200, 2160, 24)$	$1 - (25200, 540, 6)$
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 180, 1)$ $1 - (50400, 1080, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 540, 3)$ $1 - (50400, 2160, 12)$	$1 - (50400, 720, 4)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 2160, 7)$		
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 270, 1)$ $1 - (75600, 2160, 8)$	$1 - (75600, 540, 2)$	$1 - (75600, 1080, 4)$
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 216, 2)$ $1 - (30240, 2160, 20)$	$1 - (30240, 432, 4)$	$1 - (30240, 1080, 10)$
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 1080, 5)$	$1 - (60480, 2160, 10)$	
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 144, 1)$	$1 - (40320, 432, 3)$	$1 - (40320, 2160, 15)$

Table 14: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 525

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 3, 5)$ $1 - (315, 192, 320)$	$1 - (315, 24, 40)$	$1 - (315, 96, 160)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 24, 5)$ $1 - (2520, 576, 120)$	$1 - (2520, 192, 40)$	$1 - (2520, 288, 60)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 16, 15)$	$1 - (560, 144, 135)$	$1 - (560, 192, 180)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 32, 1)$ $1 - (16800, 384, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 96, 3)$ $1 - (16800, 1152, 36)$	$1 - (16800, 128, 4)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 24, 2)$ $1 - (6300, 192, 16)$ $1 - (6300, 1152, 96)$	$1 - (6300, 36, 3)$ $1 - (6300, 384, 32)$	$1 - (6300, 144, 12)$ $1 - (6300, 576, 48)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 96, 25)$	$1 - (2016, 384, 100)$	$1 - (2016, 1152, 300)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 576, 25)$	$1 - (12096, 1152, 50)$	
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 48, 1)$ $1 - (25200, 192, 4)$ $1 - (25200, 576, 12)$	$1 - (25200, 96, 2)$ $1 - (25200, 288, 6)$ $1 - (25200, 1152, 24)$	$1 - (25200, 144, 3)$ $1 - (25200, 384, 8)$
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 96, 1)$ $1 - (50400, 384, 4)$	$1 - (50400, 192, 2)$ $1 - (50400, 576, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 288, 3)$ $1 - (50400, 1152, 12)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 1152, 7)$		
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 144, 1)$ $1 - (75600, 1152, 8)$	$1 - (75600, 288, 2)$	$1 - (75600, 576, 4)$
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 288, 5)$	$1 - (30240, 1152, 20)$	
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 576, 5)$	$1 - (60480, 1152, 10)$	
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 384, 5)$	$1 - (40320, 1152, 15)$	

Table 15: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 315

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 1, 1)$ $1 - (315, 80, 80)$	$1 - (315, 10, 10)$ $1 - (315, 160, 160)$	$1 - (315, 32, 32)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 120, 15)$	$1 - (2520, 480, 60)$	$1 - (2520, 960, 120)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 80, 45)$	$1 - (560, 480, 270)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 160, 3)$	$1 - (16800, 640, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 1920, 36)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 20, 1)$ $1 - (6300, 480, 24)$	$1 - (6300, 80, 4)$ $1 - (6300, 640, 32)$	$1 - (6300, 120, 6)$ $1 - (6300, 1920, 96)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 32, 5)$ $1 - (2016, 640, 100)$	$1 - (2016, 160, 25)$	$1 - (2016, 384, 60)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 192, 5)$ $1 - (12096, 1920, 50)$	$1 - (12096, 384, 10)$	$1 - (12096, 960, 25)$
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 80, 1)$ $1 - (25200, 480, 6)$ $1 - (25200, 1920, 24)$	$1 - (25200, 160, 2)$ $1 - (25200, 640, 8)$	$1 - (25200, 320, 4)$ $1 - (25200, 960, 12)$
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 160, 1)$ $1 - (50400, 640, 4)$	$1 - (50400, 320, 2)$ $1 - (50400, 1920, 12)$	$1 - (50400, 480, 3)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 1920, 7)$		
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 240, 1)$ $1 - (75600, 1920, 8)$	$1 - (75600, 480, 2)$	$1 - (75600, 960, 4)$
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 480, 5)$	$1 - (30240, 1920, 20)$	
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 192, 1)$ $1 - (60480, 1920, 10)$	$1 - (60480, 384, 2)$	$1 - (60480, 960, 5)$
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 640, 5)$	$1 - (40320, 1920, 15)$	

Table 16: The designs by J_2 , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 100

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (315, 63, 20)$	$1 - (315, 252, 80)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (2520, 1008, 40)$	$1 - (2520, 1512, 60)$	
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (560, 56, 10)$	$1 - (560, 252, 45)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (16800, 672, 4)$	$1 - (16800, 2016, 12)$	$1 - (16800, 6048, 36)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (6300, 63, 1)$ $1 - (6300, 1512, 24)$	$1 - (6300, 378, 6)$ $1 - (6300, 2016, 32)$	$1 - (6300, 756, 12)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (2016, 2016, 1)$		
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (12096, 3024, 25)$		
$Cl(11)$	$1 - (25200, 504, 2)$ $1 - (25200, 1512, 6)$	$1 - (25200, 756, 3)$ $1 - (25200, 3024, 12)$	$1 - (25200, 1008, 4)$ $1 - (25200, 6048, 24)$
$Cl(12), Cl(19)$	$1 - (50400, 504, 1)$ $1 - (50400, 3024, 6)$	$1 - (50400, 1512, 3)$ $1 - (50400, 6048, 12)$	$1 - (50400, 2016, 4)$
$Cl(13)$	$1 - (86400, 864, 1)$	$1 - (86400, 6048, 7)$	
$Cl(14)$	$1 - (75600, 756, 1)$ $1 - (75600, 6048, 8)$	$1 - (75600, 1512, 2)$	$1 - (75600, 3024, 4)$
$Cl(15), Cl(16)$	$1 - (30240, 6048, 20)$		
$Cl(17), Cl(18)$	$1 - (60480, 3024, 5)$ $1 - (60480, 1920, 10)$	$1 - (60480, 6048, 10)$	
$Cl(20), Cl(21)$	$1 - (40320, 2016, 5)$	$1 - (40320, 6048, 15)$	

Designs from the Mathieu group M_{11}

Table 17: The designs by M_{11} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 165

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (165, 1, 1)$ $1 - (165, 24, 24)$	$1 - (165, 8, 8)$ $1 - (165, 48, 48)$	$1 - (165, 12, 12)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (440, 8, 3)$ $1 - (440, 48, 18)$	$1 - (440, 16, 6)$	$1 - (440, 24, 9)$
$Cl(4), Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (990, 6, 1)$	$1 - (990, 24, 4)$	$1 - (990, 48, 8)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (1584, 48, 5)$		
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (1320, 8, 1)$ $1 - (1320, 48, 6)$	$1 - (1320, 16, 2)$	$1 - (1320, 24, 3)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (720, 48, 11)$		

Table 18: The designs by M_{11} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 66

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (165, 10, 4)$ $1 - (165, 60, 24)$	$1 - (165, 15, 6)$	$1 - (165, 20, 8)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (440, 20, 3)$ $1 - (440, 120, 18)$	$1 - (440, 40, 6)$	$1 - (440, 60, 9)$
$Cl(4), Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (990, 30, 2)$	$1 - (990, 60, 4)$	$1 - (990, 120, 8)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (1584, 24, 1)$	$1 - (1584, 120, 5)$	
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (1320, 20, 1)$ $1 - (1320, 120, 6)$	$1 - (1320, 40, 2)$	$1 - (1320, 60, 3)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (720, 120, 11)$		

Table 19: The designs by M_{11} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 55

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (165, 9, 3)$	$1 - (165, 12, 4)$	$1 - (165, 72, 24)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (440, 8, 1)$	$1 - (440, 72, 9)$	$1 - (440, 144, 18)$
$Cl(4), Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (990, 18, 1)$ $1 - (990, 144, 8)$	$1 - (990, 36, 2)$	$1 - (990, 72, 4)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (1584, 144, 5)$		
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (1320, 24, 1)$	$1 - (1320, 72, 3)$	$1 - (1320, 144, 6)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (720, 144, 11)$		

Table 20: The designs by M_{11} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 12

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (165, 55, 4)$	$1 - (165, 110, 8)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (440, 110, 3)$	$1 - (440, 220, 6)$	
$Cl(4), Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (990, 330, 4)$	$1 - (990, 660, 8)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (1584, 132, 1)$	$1 - (1584, 660, 5)$	
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (1320, 110, 1)$ $1 - (1320, 660, 6)$	$1 - (1320, 220, 2)$	$1 - (1320, 330, 3)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (720, 60, 1)$	$1 - (720, 660, 11)$	

Table 21: The designs by M_{11} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 11

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (165, 45, 3)$	$1 - (165, 120, 8)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (440, 80, 2)$	$1 - (440, 360, 9)$	
$Cl(4), Cl(7), Cl(8)$	$1 - (990, 90, 1)$	$1 - (990, 180, 2)$	$1 - (990, 720, 8)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (1584, 144, 1)$	$1 - (1584, 720, 5)$	
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (1320, 240, 2)$	$1 - (1320, 360, 3)$	$1 - (1320, 720, 6)$
$Cl(9), Cl(10)$	$1 - (720, 720, 1)$		

Designs from the Mathieu group M_{12}

Table 22: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1320

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 3, 10)$ $1 - (396, 24, 80)$	$1 - (396, 9, 30)$ $1 - (396, 36, 120)$	$1 - (396, 18, 60)$ $1 - (396, 72, 240)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 3, 8)$ $1 - (495, 36, 96)$	$1 - (495, 18, 48)$ $1 - (495, 72, 192)$	$1 - (495, 24, 64)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 4, 3)$ $1 - (1760, 72, 54)$	$1 - (1760, 24, 18)$	$1 - (1760, 36, 27)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 2, 1)$ $1 - (2640, 24, 12)$	$1 - (2640, 8, 4)$ $1 - (2640, 36, 18)$	$1 - (2640, 18, 9)$ $1 - (2640, 72, 36)$
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 18, 8)$	$1 - (2970, 36, 16)$	$1 - (2970, 72, 32)$
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 36, 5)$	$1 - (9504, 72, 10)$	
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 6, 1)$ $1 - (7920, 36, 6)$	$1 - (7920, 18, 3)$ $1 - (7920, 72, 12)$	$1 - (7920, 24, 4)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 12, 1)$ $1 - (15840, 72, 6)$	$1 - (15840, 24, 2)$	$1 - (15840, 36, 3)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 36, 4)$	$1 - (11880, 72, 8)$	
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 72, 11)$		

Table 23: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 495

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 4, 5)$ $1 - (396, 24, 30)$	$1 - (396, 12, 15)$ $1 - (396, 48, 60)$	$1 - (396, 16, 20)$ $1 - (396, 96, 120)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 1, 1)$ $1 - (495, 12, 12)$ $1 - (495, 32, 32)$	$1 - (495, 3, 3)$ $1 - (495, 16, 16)$ $1 - (495, 48, 48)$	$1 - (495, 6, 6)$ $1 - (495, 24, 24)$ $1 - (495, 96, 96)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 32, 9)$ $1 - (1760, 192, 54)$	$1 - (1760, 64, 18)$	$1 - (1760, 96, 27)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 16, 3)$ $1 - (2640, 64, 12)$	$1 - (2640, 32, 6)$ $1 - (2640, 96, 18)$	$1 - (2640, 48, 9)$ $1 - (2640, 192, 36)$
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 6, 1)$ $1 - (2970, 48, 8)$	$1 - (2970, 12, 2)$ $1 - (2970, 96, 16)$	$1 - (2970, 24, 4)$ $1 - (2970, 192, 32)$
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 96, 5)$	$1 - (9504, 192, 10)$	
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 32, 2)$ $1 - (7920, 192, 12)$	$1 - (7920, 48, 3)$	$1 - (7920, 96, 6)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 32, 1)$ $1 - (15840, 192, 6)$	$1 - (15840, 64, 2)$	$1 - (15840, 96, 3)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 24, 1)$ $1 - (11880, 192, 8)$	$1 - (11880, 48, 2)$	$1 - (11880, 96, 4)$
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 192, 11)$		

Table 24: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 396

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 1, 1)$ $1 - (396, 30, 30)$	$1 - (396, 10, 10)$ $1 - (396, 60, 60)$	$1 - (396, 15, 15)$ $1 - (396, 120, 120)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 15, 12)$ $1 - (495, 120, 96)$	$1 - (495, 30, 24)$	$1 - (495, 60, 48)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 40, 9)$	$1 - (1760, 120, 27)$	$1 - (1760, 240, 54)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 20, 3)$ $1 - (2640, 120, 18)$	$1 - (2640, 60, 9)$ $1 - (2640, 240, 36)$	$1 - (2640, 80, 12)$
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 30, 4)$ $1 - (2970, 240, 32)$	$1 - (2970, 60, 8)$	$1 - (2970, 120, 16)$
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 24, 1)$	$1 - (9504, 120, 5)$	$1 - (9504, 240, 10)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 20, 1)$ $1 - (7920, 240, 12)$	$1 - (7920, 60, 3)$	$1 - (7920, 120, 6)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 120, 3)$	$1 - (15840, 240, 6)$	
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 60, 2)$	$1 - (11880, 120, 4)$	$1 - (11880, 240, 8)$
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 240, 11)$		

Table 25: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 220

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 72, 40)$	$1 - (396, 108, 60)$	$1 - (396, 216, 120)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 9, 4)$ $1 - (495, 72, 32)$	$1 - (495, 36, 16)$ $1 - (495, 108, 48)$	$1 - (495, 54, 24)$ $1 - (495, 216, 96)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 8, 1)$ $1 - (1760, 216, 27)$	$1 - (1760, 24, 3)$ $1 - (1760, 432, 54)$	$1 - (1760, 72, 9)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 48, 4)$	$1 - (2640, 144, 12)$	$1 - (2640, 432, 36)$
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 54, 4)$ $1 - (2970, 432, 32)$	$1 - (2970, 108, 8)$	$1 - (2970, 216, 16)$
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 432, 10)$		
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 144, 4)$	$1 - (7920, 432, 12)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 72, 1)$ $1 - (15840, 432, 6)$	$1 - (15840, 144, 2)$	$1 - (15840, 216, 3)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 54, 1)$ $1 - (11880, 432, 8)$	$1 - (11880, 108, 2)$	$1 - (11880, 216, 4)$
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 432, 11)$		

Table 26: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 144

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 55, 20)$	$1 - (396, 66, 24)$	$1 - (396, 165, 60)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 165, 48)$ $1 - (495, 330, 96)$		
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 220, 18)$ $1 - (1760, 660, 54)$		
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 55, 3)$ $1 - (2640, 330, 18)$	$1 - (2640, 110, 6)$ $1 - (2640, 660, 36)$	$1 - (2640, 220, 12)$
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 330, 16)$ $1 - (2970, 660, 32)$		
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 132, 2)$	$1 - (9504, 330, 5)$	$1 - (9504, 660, 10)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 110, 2)$ $1 - (7920, 660, 12)$	$1 - (7920, 165, 3)$	$1 - (7920, 330, 6)$
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 660, 6)$		
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 660, 8)$		
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 60, 1)$	$1 - (8640, 660, 11)$	

Table 27: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 66

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 36, 6)$	$1 - (396, 180, 30)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 30, 4)$ $1 - (495, 240, 32)$	$1 - (495, 45, 6)$	$1 - (495, 180, 24)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 80, 3)$	$1 - (1760, 240, 9)$	$1 - (1760, 720, 27)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 480, 12)$	$1 - (2640, 720, 18)$	$1 - (2640, 1440, 36)$
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 90, 2)$ $1 - (2970, 720, 16)$	$1 - (2970, 180, 4)$ $1 - (2970, 1440, 32)$	$1 - (2970, 360, 8)$
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 144, 1)$	$1 - (9504, 720, 5)$	$1 - (9504, 1440, 10)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 720, 6)$	$1 - (7920, 1440, 12)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 240, 1)$ $1 - (15840, 1440, 6)$	$1 - (15840, 480, 2)$	$1 - (15840, 720, 3)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 180, 1)$ $1 - (11880, 1440, 8)$	$1 - (11880, 360, 2)$	$1 - (11880, 720, 4)$
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 1440, 11)$		

Table 28: The designs by M_{12} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 12

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (396, 396, 1)$		
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (495, 165, 4)$	$1 - (495, 330, 8)$	
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (1760, 440, 3)$	$1 - (1760, 1320, 9)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (2640, 2640, 1)$		
$Cl(6), Cl(7)$	$1 - (2970, 990, 4)$	$1 - (2970, 1980, 8)$	
$Cl(8), Cl(13)$	$1 - (9504, 1584, 2)$	$1 - (9504, 7920, 10)$	
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (7920, 7920, 1)$		
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (15840, 1320, 1)$ $1 - (15840, 7920, 6)$	$1 - (15840, 2640, 2)$	$1 - (15840, 3960, 3)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (11880, 990, 1)$ $1 - (11880, 7920, 8)$	$1 - (11880, 1980, 2)$	$1 - (11880, 3960, 4)$
$Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (8640, 720, 1)$	$1 - (8640, 7920, 11)$	

Designs from the Mathieu group M_{22}

Table 29: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 672

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 55, 32)$ $1 - (1155, 330, 192)$	$1 - (1155, 110, 64)$	$1 - (1155, 165, 96)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 110, 6)$ $1 - (12320, 660, 36)$	$1 - (12320, 220, 12)$	$1 - (12320, 330, 18)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 330, 16)$	$1 - (13860, 660, 32)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 330, 8)$	$1 - (27720, 660, 16)$	
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 132, 1)$	$1 - (88704, 660, 5)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 110, 2)$	$1 - (36960, 330, 6)$	$1 - (36960, 660, 12)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 660, 7)$		
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 330, 4)$	$1 - (55440, 660, 8)$	
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 60, 1)$	$1 - (40320, 660, 11)$	

Table 30: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 616

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 30, 16)$ $1 - (1155, 180, 96)$	$1 - (1155, 45, 24)$ $1 - (1155, 360, 192)$	$1 - (1155, 90, 48)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 80, 4)$ $1 - (12320, 720, 36)$	$1 - (12320, 240, 12)$	$1 - (12320, 360, 18)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 90, 4)$ $1 - (13860, 720, 32)$	$1 - (13860, 180, 8)$	$1 - (13860, 360, 16)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 180, 4)$	$1 - (27720, 360, 8)$	$1 - (27720, 720, 16)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 144, 1)$	$1 - (88704, 720, 5)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 240, 4)$	$1 - (36960, 360, 6)$	$1 - (36960, 720, 12)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 720, 7)$		
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 90, 1)$ $1 - (55440, 720, 8)$	$1 - (55440, 180, 2)$	$1 - (55440, 360, 4)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 720, 11)$		

Table 31: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 176

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 105, 16)$	$1 - (1155, 315, 48)$	$1 - (1155, 630, 96)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 70, 1)$ $1 - (12320, 840, 12)$	$1 - (12320, 210, 3)$ $1 - (12320, 1260, 18)$	$1 - (12320, 280, 4)$ $1 - (12320, 2520, 36)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 1260, 16)$	$1 - (13860, 2520, 32)$	
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 630, 4)$	$1 - (27720, 1260, 8)$	$1 - (27720, 2520, 16)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 504, 1)$	$1 - (88704, 2520, 5)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 210, 1)$ $1 - (36960, 1260, 6)$	$1 - (36960, 630, 3)$ $1 - (36960, 2520, 12)$	$1 - (36960, 840, 4)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 360, 1)$	$1 - (63360, 2520, 7)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 1260, 4)$	$1 - (55440, 2520, 8)$	
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 2520, 11)$		

Table 32: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 330

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 7, 2)$ $1 - (1155, 168, 48)$	$1 - (1155, 42, 12)$ $1 - (1155, 672, 192)$	$1 - (1155, 56, 16)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 112, 3)$ $1 - (12320, 672, 18)$	$1 - (12320, 224, 6)$ $1 - (12320, 1344, 36)$	$1 - (12320, 448, 12)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 84, 2)$ $1 - (13860, 672, 16)$	$1 - (13860, 168, 4)$ $1 - (13860, 1344, 32)$	$1 - (13860, 336, 8)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 168, 2)$ $1 - (27720, 1344, 16)$	$1 - (27720, 336, 4)$	$1 - (27720, 672, 8)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 1344, 5)$		
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 224, 2)$ $1 - (36960, 1344, 12)$	$1 - (36960, 336, 3)$	$1 - (36960, 672, 6)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 192, 1)$	$1 - (63360, 1344, 7)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 336, 2)$	$1 - (55440, 672, 4)$	$1 - (55440, 1344, 8)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 1344, 11)$		

Table 33: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 231

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 15, 3)$ $1 - (1155, 240, 48)$	$1 - (1155, 40, 8)$ $1 - (1155, 320, 64)$	$1 - (1155, 60, 12)$ $1 - (1155, 480, 96)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 160, 3)$ $1 - (12320, 640, 12)$	$1 - (12320, 320, 6)$ $1 - (12320, 960, 18)$	$1 - (12320, 480, 9)$ $1 - (12320, 1920, 36)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 60, 1)$ $1 - (13860, 280, 8)$	$1 - (13860, 120, 2)$ $1 - (13860, 960, 16)$	$1 - (13860, 240, 4)$ $1 - (13860, 1920, 32)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 120, 1)$ $1 - (27720, 960, 8)$	$1 - (27720, 240, 2)$ $1 - (27720, 1920, 16)$	$1 - (27720, 480, 4)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 384, 1)$	$1 - (88704, 1920, 5)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 320, 2)$ $1 - (36960, 1920, 12)$	$1 - (36960, 480, 3)$	$1 - (36960, 960, 6)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 1920, 7)$		
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 240, 1)$ $1 - (55440, 1920, 8)$	$1 - (55440, 480, 2)$	$1 - (55440, 960, 4)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 1920, 11)$		

Table 34: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 77

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 15, 1)$ $1 - (1155, 720, 48)$	$1 - (1155, 180, 12)$	$1 - (1155, 240, 16)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 160, 1)$ $1 - (12320, 2880, 18)$	$1 - (12320, 640, 4)$	$1 - (12320, 1920, 12)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 180, 1)$ $1 - (13860, 2880, 16)$	$1 - (13860, 720, 4)$ $1 - (13860, 5760, 32)$	$1 - (13860, 1440, 8)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 360, 1)$ $1 - (27720, 5760, 16)$	$1 - (27720, 1440, 4)$	$1 - (27720, 2880, 8)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 1152, 1)$	$1 - (88704, 5760, 5)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 480, 1)$ $1 - (36960, 5760, 12)$	$1 - (36960, 1920, 4)$	$1 - (36960, 2880, 6)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 5760, 7)$		
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 720, 1)$ $1 - (55440, 5760, 8)$	$1 - (55440, 1440, 2)$	$1 - (55440, 2880, 4)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 5760, 11)$		

Table 35: The designs by M_{22} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 22

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (1155, 315, 6)$	$1 - (1155, 840, 16)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (12320, 1680, 3)$	$1 - (12320, 2240, 4)$	$1 - (12320, 6720, 12)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (13860, 2520, 4)$	$1 - (13860, 1260, 2)$	$1 - (13860, 10080, 16)$
$Cl(5)$	$1 - (27720, 1260, 1)$	$1 - (27720, 5040, 4)$	$1 - (27720, 20160, 16)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (88704, 4032, 1)$	$1 - (88704, 20160, 5)$	
$Cl(7)$	$1 - (36960, 5040, 3)$	$1 - (36960, 6720, 4)$	$1 - (36960, 20160, 12)$
$Cl(8), Cl(9)$	$1 - (63360, 2880, 1)$	$1 - (63360, 20160, 7)$	
$Cl(10)$	$1 - (55440, 5040, 2)$	$1 - (55440, 10080, 4)$	$1 - (55440, 20160, 8)$
$Cl(11), Cl(12)$	$1 - (40320, 20160, 11)$		

Designs from the Mathieu group M_{23}

Table 36: The designs by M_{23} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 40230

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (3795, 253, 2688)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (56672, 253, 180)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (318780, 253, 32)$
$Cl(5), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (680064, 253, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (850080, 253, 12)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8), Cl(12), Cl(13)$	$1 - (728640, 253, 14)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (1275120, 253, 8)$
$Cl(10), Cl(11)$	$1 - (927360, 23, 1)$ $1 - (927360, 253, 11)$
$Cl(16), Cl(17)$	$1 - (443520, 11, 1)$ $1 - (443520, 253, 23)$

Table 37: The designs by M_{23} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 12

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (3795, 165, 56)$ $1 - (3795, 330, 112)$ $1 - (3795, 990, 336)$ $1 - (3795, 1980, 672)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (56672, 440, 10)$ $1 - (56672, 792, 18)$ $1 - (56672, 1320, 30)$ $1 - (56672, 2640, 60)$ $1 - (56672, 3960, 90)$ $1 - (56672, 7920, 180)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (318780, 990, 4)$ $1 - (318780, 1980, 8)$ $1 - (318780, 3960, 16)$ $1 - (318780, 7920, 32)$
$Cl(5), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (680064, 1584, 3)$ $1 - (680064, 2640, 5)$ $1 - (680064, 7920, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (850080, 1320, 2)$ $1 - (850080, 2640, 4)$ $1 - (850080, 3960, 6)$ $1 - (850080, 7920, 12)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8), Cl(12), Cl(13)$	$1 - (728640, 3960, 7)$ $1 - (728640, 7920, 14)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (1275120, 990, 1)$ $1 - (1275120, 1980, 2)$ $1 - (1275120, 3960, 4)$ $1 - (1275120, 7920, 8)$
$Cl(10), Cl(11)$	$1 - (927360, 720, 1)$ $1 - (927360, 7920, 11)$
$Cl(16), Cl(17)$	$1 - (443520, 7920, 23)$

Table 38: The designs by M_{23} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 1771

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (3795, 15, 7)$ $1 - (3795, 60, 28)$ $1 - (3795, 120, 56)$ $1 - (3795, 240, 112)$ $1 - (3795, 720, 336)$ $1 - (3795, 960, 448)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (56672, 32, 1)$ $1 - (56672, 160, 5)$ $1 - (56672, 320, 10)$ $1 - (56672, 480, 15)$ $1 - (56672, 960, 30)$ $1 - (56672, 1440, 45)$ $1 - (56672, 1920, 60)$ $1 - (56672, 2880, 90)$ $1 - (56672, 5760, 180)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (318780, 180, 1)$ $1 - (318780, 360, 2)$ $1 - (318780, 720, 4)$ $1 - (318780, 1440, 8)$ $1 - (318780, 2880, 16)$ $1 - (318780, 5760, 32)$
$Cl(5), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (680064, 384, 1)$ $1 - (680064, 1920, 5)$ $1 - (680064, 5760, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (850080, 480, 1)$ $1 - (850080, 960, 2)$ $1 - (850080, 1440, 3)$ $1 - (850080, 1920, 4)$ $1 - (850080, 2880, 6)$ $1 - (850080, 5760, 12)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8), Cl(12), Cl(13)$	$1 - (728640, 2880, 7)$ $1 - (728640, 5760, 14)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (1275120, 720, 1)$ $1 - (1275120, 1440, 2)$ $1 - (1275120, 2880, 4)$ $1 - (1275120, 5760, 8)$
$Cl(10), Cl(11)$	$1 - (927360, 5760, 11)$
$Cl(16), Cl(17)$	$1 - (443520, 5760, 23)$

Table 39: The designs by M_{23} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 506

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (3795, 105, 14)$ $1 - (3795, 840, 112)$	$1 - (3795, 120, 16)$ $1 - (3795, 2520, 336)$	$1 - (3795, 210, 28)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (56672, 112, 1)$ $1 - (56672, 3360, 30)$	$1 - (56672, 1120, 10)$ $1 - (56672, 6720, 60)$	$1 - (56672, 1680, 15)$ $1 - (56672, 10080, 90)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (318780, 1260, 2)$ $1 - (318780, 10080, 16)$	$1 - (318780, 2520, 4)$ $1 - (318780, 20160, 32)$	$1 - (318780, 5040, 8)$
$Cl(5), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (680064, 1344, 1)$	$1 - (680064, 6720, 5)$	$1 - (680064, 20160, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (850080, 1680, 1)$ $1 - (850080, 6720, 4)$	$1 - (850080, 3360, 2)$ $1 - (850080, 10080, 6)$	$1 - (850080, 5040, 3)$ $1 - (850080, 20160, 12)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8), Cl(12), Cl(13)$	$1 - (728640, 2880, 2)$	$1 - (728640, 10080, 7)$	$1 - (728640, 20160, 14)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (1275120, 5040, 2)$	$1 - (1275120, 10080, 4)$	$1 - (1275120, 20160, 8)$
$Cl(10), Cl(11)$	$1 - (927360, 20160, 11)$		
$Cl(16), Cl(17)$	$1 - (443520, 20160, 23)$		

Table 40: The designs by M_{23} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 253

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (3795, 15, 1)$ $1 - (3795, 420, 28)$	$1 - (3795, 120, 8)$ $1 - (3795, 1680, 112)$	$1 - (3795, 315, 21)$
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (56672, 672, 3)$ $1 - (56672, 3360, 15)$ $1 - (56672, 10080, 45)$	$1 - (56672, 1120, 5)$ $1 - (56672, 4032, 18)$ $1 - (56672, 13440, 60)$	$1 - (56672, 2240, 10)$ $1 - (56672, 6720, 30)$ $1 - (56672, 20160, 90)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (318780, 1260, 1)$ $1 - (318780, 10080, 8)$	$1 - (318780, 2520, 2)$ $1 - (318780, 20160, 16)$	$1 - (318780, 5040, 4)$ $1 - (318780, 40320, 32)$
$Cl(5), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (680064, 8064, 3)$	$1 - (680064, 13440, 5)$	$1 - (680064, 40320, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (850080, 3360, 1)$ $1 - (850080, 13440, 4)$	$1 - (850080, 6720, 2)$ $1 - (850080, 20160, 6)$	$1 - (850080, 10080, 3)$ $1 - (850080, 40320, 12)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8), Cl(12), Cl(13)$	$1 - (728640, 2880, 1)$	$1 - (728640, 20160, 7)$	$1 - (728640, 40320, 14)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (1275120, 5040, 1)$ $1 - (1275120, 40320, 8)$	$1 - (1275120, 10080, 2)$	$1 - (1275120, 20160, 4)$
$Cl(10), Cl(11)$	$1 - (927360, 40320, 11)$		
$Cl(16), Cl(17)$	$1 - (443520, 40320, 23)$		

Table 41: The designs by M_{23} , where H is a maximal subgroup with index 23

Conjugacy classes $Cl(i)$	Designs $1 - (v, k, \lambda)$		
$Cl(2)$	$1 - (3795, 1155, 7)$	$1 - (3795, 2640, 16)$	
$Cl(3)$	$1 - (56672, 7392, 3)$	$1 - (56672, 12320, 5)$	$1 - (56672, 36960, 15)$
$Cl(4)$	$1 - (318780, 13860, 1)$ $1 - (318780, 221760, 16)$	$1 - (318780, 27720, 2)$	$1 - (318780, 55440, 4)$
$Cl(5), Cl(14), Cl(15)$	$1 - (680064, 88704, 3)$	$1 - (680064, 147840, 5)$	$1 - (680064, 443520, 15)$
$Cl(6)$	$1 - (850080, 36960, 1)$ $1 - (850080, 443520, 12)$	$1 - (850080, 110880, 3)$	$1 - (850080, 147840, 4)$
$Cl(7), Cl(8), Cl(12), Cl(13)$	$1 - (728640, 63360, 2)$	$1 - (728640, 221760, 7)$	$1 - (728640, 443520, 14)$
$Cl(9)$	$1 - (1275120, 55440, 1)$ $1 - (1275120, 443520, 8)$	$1 - (1275120, 110880, 2)$	$1 - (1275120, 221760, 4)$
$Cl(10), Cl(11)$	$1 - (927360, 40320, 1)$	$1 - (927360, 443520, 11)$	
$Cl(16), Cl(17)$	$1 - (443520, 443520, 1)$		